

We are entering a new era where, instead of going on the internet, we will go into the spatial web, which will eventually eliminate the boundaries between digital and physical.

The spatial web: Interconnecting people, places, things and AI for a smarter world

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The boundaries between our digital and physical worlds are becoming increasingly blurred. We are entering a new era where compute and data will progressively come into the world: instead of going on the Internet, we will be going into a new internet – the emerging world of the “spatial web”, sometimes called the outernet, web 3.0, industry 4.0, society 5.0 or the “metaverse”, depending on your specific vantage point.

The spatial web is the next evolution in computing and information technology, which will eventually eliminate the boundary between digital content and physical objects that we know today. It raises challenges and creates opportunities to work towards a more transparent, interoperable, trustworthy, secure and compliant cyber-physical network of people, places and things.

Key insights

- It is necessary to integrate disparate technologies into a cohesive network that is as coherent with our logical understanding of the world as it is with the physical features of the world.
- An integrated operational framework is required to contextualize and synchronize data sources while making them interoperable.
- This framework needs to be built on new standards while leveraging legacy systems. It will have to address challenges in terms of context, space, operations and legislation.
- The new standards hinge on fundamental requirements around communication, interoperability, trust, adaptability and execution.

Key recommendations

- Fund research and development (R&D) and pilots to showcase the horizontal integration capabilities of the new standards.
- Create a “world model” based on spatial and multidimensional data and metadata that allows for impactful scenario simulations (e.g. decarbonization and circular economy use cases). This model can replicate the intelligence loop of sensing, modelling, simulating, acting and adapting to changes in the context and the environment.
- Raise awareness about the need for contextual and adaptive computing and metadata standardization.
- Upskill talent to master the spatial web standards implementation and methodology.
- Explore and contribute to the IEEE Spatial Web WG (P2874): <https://sagroups.ieee.org/2874/>
- Promote organizations and events, such as competence networks and hackathons, to raise awareness and drive the collaboration and change required for further adoption of the spatial web standards.
- Create a dedicated fund for developing applications and start-ups using spatial web standards.

Challenges and requirements

One of the most urgent and difficult problems in computing is poor interoperability between software and hardware. It is necessary to integrate these disparate but increasingly mutually reliant technologies into a unified and cohesive network for an information exchange that is as coherent with our *logical understanding* of the world as it is with the *physical features* of the world.

With a growing suite of advancing and emerging technologies coming together in all areas of our society and economy, the need to make sense of disparate data has never been greater. The convergence of autonomous vehicles, drones and bots, internet of things (IoT) sensors, extended reality (XR), sovereign identity, digital transactions, 5G, plus the need for an artificial intelligence system that can safely orchestrate all their activities, necessitate new technologies and protocols. An integrated operational framework and system is needed to contextualize, synchronize and make interoperable these disparate data sources about people, places, assets and things.

This operational framework needs to be built on new standards while leveraging legacy systems to address four fundamental new challenges to successfully govern activities in the real and virtual world.

- 1) The context challenge of internetworking functionalities and data between humans, machines, and objects, and the heterogeneous and siloed systems operating them.
- 2) The spatial challenge of delineating and coordinating activities between humans, machines, and objects in a multidimensional way (3D, 4D, cost, temperature, safety, etc.).
- 3) The operational challenge of synchronizing the flow of information and activities across spaces, humans, machines, and objects.
- 4) The legislative challenge of creating and maintaining digital versions of policies and legislation, and making them machine readable, machine sharable and machine executable.

The spatial web initiative and IEEE P2874 standards

The Spatial Web Foundation [1] has defined a contextual model and communication protocol that captures multi-dimension data interoperability. These standards allow systems to share a more complete and coherent understanding of activities and to continuously self-optimize. They hinge on several fundamental requirements that build upon each other:

- 1) **Communication:** a common query language in which to interface.
- 2) **Interoperability:** a common data model in which to map context.
- 3) **Trust:** verifiable data lineage, credentials, and governance.
- 4) **Adaptability:** flexible logic to simulate and adjust.
- 5) **Execution:** ability to orchestrate tasks and resources.

They are being standardized within the IEEE WG P2874 [2], namely:

- HSML - Hyperspace Modeling Language
 - A common data model that enables adaptive intelligence at scale.
 - A standard that models spatial and hyperdimensional relationships which can exist between any base elements and their purpose.
- HSTP - Hyperspace Transaction Protocol
 - Multi-dimensional range query.
 - A contracting protocol that queries that language and sends and receives the common language's data.
 - Protocols allowing stakeholders to govern identities, activities and spaces and location in an interoperable way and across data domains.
 - Governs interactions between parties to ensure privacy and security.

Note that IEEE has designated both the HSML and HSTP protocols as a “public imperative”. This designation is typically reserved for critical public infrastructure like nuclear energy, smart grids, and voting machines.

Context awareness: the missing link to a smarter cyber-physical architecture

The vision of a smarter cyber-physical infrastructure requires full awareness of policy and context. AI systems, for instance, will require context-making to improve performance and explainability: they need to be policy-aware and context-aware. Data needs to be put into context for IoT and cyber-physical systems to remain relevant and adaptive to changes in use cases and scenarios.

Context can be defined as follows:

- Context is multi-dimensional. It needs to describe identities, activities, and spaces and places. That encompasses the following dimensions:
 - semantic (meaning and logic)
 - spatial (physical and situational)
 - societal (values and value)
 - systems (networks and ecosystems)
- Context needs to:
 - be stateful
 - be machine readable and executable
 - be shareable between heterogeneous networks, devices and applications
 - maintain coherence over time and space for all the actors/edges involved in a use case
- Context is represented by models of metadata that describe the activities of people, places and things over time. Context needs to be shared between networks of heterogeneous devices and applications empowering them to proactively offer enriched, situation-aware and usable content, instructions and experiences.
- Context is made up of the elements of relationships between identities, activities, spaces and places – commonly known as the *who, what, when, where, how* and *why* of any scenario, situation or circumstance. The answers to these questions are often stored in different data silos and different data spaces. They need to be made interoperable and are key to building a smarter cyber-physical infrastructure that is privacy preserving, secure interoperable and compliant by design.

The challenges in modelling context are linked to – although not limited to – a set of constraints: they need to represent the relationship between the identity of the

Figure 1: Smart cyber physical infrastructure

Figure 2: HSML modeling elements. Source: The Spatial Web Foundation

Figure 3: HSML elements. Source: The Spatial Web Foundation

actor, the scope and authorization of their permitted activities, and the place and time where they may happen. HSML coherently describes and maintains the *where* and *when* of any scenario (dimensions, space, time and channel), the *why* and *how* (i.e. conditions or governance – right, credential, claim and activity), and the *who* and *what* (i.e. objects – authority, domain, actor and asset) shareable and addressable by multiple competing AI algorithms that can maintain their coherence at scale.

Spatial domains: a paradigm shift in anchoring data in space

Spatial domains are digital titles linked to 3D volumetric locations, such as buildings, ports, streets, or larger regions, such as cities, states, continents and trading blocs. Spatial subdomains represent subspaces that have a holonic structure, which allows for the orchestration of hierarchical rights and policies.

Spatial domains enable secure management of digitally mediated rights and permissions for:

- who/what is authorized to access the domain.
- what content or data is available to view.
- who/what kind of activities are allowed.
- who can publish and modify content.
- who can transact or interact with it.

Rules and regulations

Spatial domains contain all the rules, rights, permissions and fees associated with a geospatial region as defined by their owner or authority. This results in a governance layer of geospatial information written in HSML that can be queried by actors as they approach and move through them.

3D model

The 3D model contains all the geometries, addresses, spatial anchors, location of IoT devices, and any subdomains. The 3D model is dynamic and can be updated in real time as local conditions change. A visual digital twin can be used to represent the spatial domain and the activities happening within it.

Policy awareness: from analogue to adaptive digital law

How can we maintain and enforce policies that can be interpreted and shared by machines and humans? Existing regulations have traditionally been drafted by humans, for humans, with little regard for interpretability and executability by machines. There is tremendous value in seeking to bridge the gap between the traditional way of drafting and publishing regulations (i.e. *by humans, for humans*) and having machine-readable and machine-executable regulation (i.e. *by humans, for machines*) especially in the context of autonomous mobility scenarios.

Translating existing regulations into machine-interpretable and machine-executable code will allow us to govern the behaviour of machines in a policy-compliant way and dynamically adapt that behaviour as policies change and evolve over time. More generally, the challenge is to discover where and when technology can replace humans when it comes to interpretation, and where and why not.

The FF2020 Horizon Europe project [3] developed a geospatial infrastructure using the draft IEEE Spatial Web standards and protocols (HSML and HSTP) to govern actions within the domain of urban air mobility to enforce rules and policies systematically. This solution allows current laws to be parsed into machine-readable models and interpreted programmatically, reducing the human interpretation of laws and guidelines into more binary statements.

The solution takes the legal text and constructs ontologies and context from automated natural language processing and machine learning methodologies. These are then used to construct machine-readable representations of specific legal scenarios. This information is then parsed into HSML, where it is combined with other sources of information (such as IoT devices, user input, cameras, drones, etc.) that enable the AI powering a drone to be able to understand and comply with laws and conditions.

Figure 4: Spatial domains. Source: The Spatial Web Foundation

Figure 5: Indoor spatial domains. Source: The Spatial Web Foundation

Figure 6: Outdoor spatial domains. Source: The Spatial Web Foundation

Figure 7: Building block for hyperdimensional contextual interoperability. Source: The Spatial Web Foundation

For example, harmonized liability rules for drones are lacking at the European Union (EU) level (U-spaces). Consequently, liability law is governed by the traditional rules at the national (member-state) level. An innovation, therefore, lies in (1) the development of liability rules that are (2) machine-interpretable and machine-executable.

Moreover, regulation is subject to change, and it is often multi-layered, meaning that regulatory bodies at different levels (e.g. EU level, state level, municipality level and company level) jointly contribute to a specific type of regulation. As a result, different pieces of regulation may consist of different languages.

To make a regulation machine-interpretable and machine-executable, and to make any interpretation model scalable, a semantic representation that accommodates regulatory changes and regulation at different levels and in different languages needs to be available. The technological challenge lies in the development of a suitable semantic representation that is applicable to specific geolocations.

Several laws that have been converted into HSML, including rules about dynamically changing variables, have been tested in real-world flight environments. We translated existing EU laws for urban air mobility into HSML, ensuring that the proposed actions and flight plans automati-

cally conform to the set of parsed rules and regulations at play:

- The consortium ensured that HSML could accommodate the vast array of prohibitive and deontic laws found in the EU literature.
- The consortium worked with legal experts to ensure that the assumptions made during the translation process respected existing interpretations of the relevant laws.
- The consortium worked to provide a mechanism for suggesting legal innovations when a machine-readable format cannot straightforwardly accommodate the ambiguity of laws.

Building blocks for hyperdimensional and contextual interoperability

The figure below shows a building block that enables hyperdimensional contextual interoperability. It includes the following capabilities:

- Internetworking spatial domains and context sharing using machine understandable and executable policies
- Operational AI-based assistance, e.g. cross-domain search, AI-based simulation and recommendation, and policy-based AI execution

KOSM, the AI operating system developed by VERSES, is an example of a building block implementation: It can be described as an operating system built upon HSML and HSTP that allows for the

deployment of artificial intelligence applications in a way that integrates physical, logical, and operational meta-data. KOSM thereby allows for the autonomous, efficient, compliant and secure flow of people and things in the real world and/or in a metaverse.

References

- [1] The Spatial Web Foundation: <https://spatialwebfoundation.org/>
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